

COMPARISON OF CORONARY PLAQUE CHARACTERISTICS BETWEEN DIABETIC AND NON-DIABETIC PATIENTS BY COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY ANGIOGRAPHY

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Abstract

Background: Coronary artery disease (CAD) occurs due to plaque buildup, restricting blood flow. Diabetes worsens this, increasing plaque burden and risk. Computed tomography angiography (CTA) is a non-invasive tool to assess plaque characteristics.

Objective: This study aims to compare coronary plaque characteristics between diabetic and non-diabetic patients by using CT angiography.

Methodology: The research was conducted at Fatima Memorial Hospital in the radiology department, involving patients with suspected coronary artery disease. Both diabetic and non-diabetic patients underwent coronary CT angiography to assess plaque characteristics.

Results: A total of 87 patients aged 40–74 years (mean age: 55.23 ± 8.38 years) were included. Non-diabetic patients frequently showed no involvement in multiple arterial segments, particularly in LCA distal ($n = 32$), RCA proximal ($n = 40$), and RCA distal ($n = 37$). In contrast, a greater percentage of moderate to severe involvement was seen in diabetics across a number of segments. Notably, diabetics were more likely to have moderate RCA mid ($n = 4$) and LCA mid ($n = 7$) involvement. Only non-diabetics showed occlusion in the LCA mid and LCA segments. Although it was still present in both groups, collateral formation was more noticeable in non-diabetics for LCA distal. Most of the sample (62.1%) had RCA dominant anatomy. Despite having a lower overall cohort representation, diabetics generally showed a tendency toward more diffuse and severe arterial involvement.

Conclusion: Increased coronary artery involvement severity is linked to diabetes, especially in the mid and distal segments of both the LCA and the RCA. These results highlight the necessity of aggressive risk factor modification and early detection strategies in diabetic populations in order to slow the progression of advanced coronary artery disease.

INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery disease (CAD) is a condition where the arteries carry blood to the heart become narrowed or obstructed owing to plaque formation, this reduces blood flow and oxygen to the heart. CAD poses a huge challenge and is a major source of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Among the many risk factors, diabetes mellitus (DM) is the one that is responsible for promoting accelerated atherosclerosis, thereby placing diabetic patients at risk for more dangerous types of CAD¹.

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder defined by excessive blood glucose levels, either due to low insulin production (Type 1) or the body's poor utilization of insulin (Type 2)². Diabetic patients have been consistently shown to have a higher prevalence of obstructive CAD, higher plaque burden, and more complex plaque morphology compared to their non-diabetic counterparts. Individuals with diabetes mellitus, who face an elevated risk of developing CAD and experiencing more severe outcomes³.

Studies have shown that diabetic patients are more likely to develop vulnerable plaque characteristics, such as positive remodeling and low-attenuation plaques, which are associated with an increased risk of acute coronary events⁶. Furthermore, the presence of diabetes is linked to higher annual rates of adverse cardiovascular outcomes, including mortality and myocardial infarction⁷. Recent research has demonstrated that genetic influences could also contribute to the modulation of CAD risk in diabetic patients. There are specific genetic polymorphisms that have been recognized as possible etiologies of the enhanced susceptibility of diabetic patients to coronary artery disease. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of CAD in the context of diabetes and emphasize the need for comprehensive risk assessment and management strategies⁸.

By utilizing CTA, healthcare providers can gain insights into the extent and nature of coronary atherosclerosis in diabetic patients, potentially identifying high-risk features before they manifest as acute coronary events¹¹. Despite its diagnostic advantages, CTA remains underutilized in routine clinical practice for diabetic patients, limiting its role in early risk stratification. This non-invasive approach aligns well with the need for comprehensive cardiovascular risk assessment in the diabetic

population, offering a means to tailor preventive strategies and interventions based on individual plaque profiles¹².

This study aims to compare coronary plaque burden and composition between symptomatic diabetic and non-diabetic patients using CT angiography (CTA). The findings revealed that diabetic patients had a higher prevalence of obstructive coronary artery disease and a greater number of coronary segments with mixed plaques compared to non-diabetics. We hypothesize that diabetic patients will exhibit a higher plaque burden and a greater prevalence of vulnerable plaques, potentially explaining their increased mortality rates from CAD. The study highlights the potential of CTA in identifying high-risk plaques in diabetic patients, which could inform more aggressive management strategies,

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was a cross-sectional study and its all data was collected from Fatima Memorial Hospital Lahore. The duration of this study is 4 months after the approval of synopsis. The Sample size used in this study was calculated at 95% level of confidence and 5% margin of error. The prevalence of Coronary plaque is 6% and the sample size for this study is 87. The inclusion criteria contain age group of Diabetic and non-diabetic patients is from 40-74. The patient undergo Computer Tomography Angiography for suspected Coronary artery disease. The exclusion criteria suggest Previous Coronary interventions, chronic Kidney Disease Severe Valvular Heart disease Equipments: Multislice or 128 slices Computer tomography angiography

Scanning Technique:

Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography (CTCA) was performed on all recruited patients using a multi-slice CT scanner with prospective or retrospective ECG gating based on heart rate. The Coronary Artery Calcium (CAC) score was determined using a non-contrast scan, and the plaque was evaluated using contrast-enhanced CTCA. A single breath-hold was utilized for picture acquisition, and intravenous iodinated contrast was utilized to reduce motion artifacts. Using thin slices of the reconstructed images, the presence, location, and

composition (calcified, non-calcified, and mixed) of coronary artery plaque in the major coronary vessels were evaluated. Using certain post-processing tools,

qualified cardiologists or radiologists interpreted each image.

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	87	40.00	74.00	55.2299	8.37591

Table 1: Representing the descriptive statistics of age. The descriptive statistics for the age of the participants (N = 87). The minimum and maximum ages were 40 and 74 years, respectively, with a mean

age of 55.23 years (SD ± 8.38). This reflects a middle to older adult population, which is relevant for understanding the clinical implications of the study outcomes.

Graph 1 : Representing the Gender distribution of study participants

Out of 87 individuals, 67.8% (n = 59) were male and 32.2% (n = 28) were female. This shows a male

predominance in the study sample, which may influence the generalizability of the findings.

Diabetic Status * LADA proximal Cross tabulation							
Count		LADA proximal					Total
		No	Mild	moderate	severe	occlusion	
Diabetic Status	NO	21	11	17	7	2	58
	YES	5	4	12	7	1	29
Total		26	15	29	14	3	87

Table 2: Representing the Cross-tabulation between diabetic status and LADA proximal arterial involvement

Graph 2: Representing the Cross-tabulation between diabetic status and LADA proximal arterial involvement

Among the non-diabetic group (n = 58), the most common finding was moderate involvement (n = 17), followed by mild (n = 11), no involvement (n = 21), severe (n = 7), and occlusion (n = 2). In diabetic patients (n = 29), moderate involvement (n = 12) was also the most frequent, followed by no involvement (n = 5), mild (n = 4), severe (n = 7), and occlusion (n = 1). These results suggest a higher proportion of moderate to severe involvement in diabetic individuals. Among non-diabetics (n = 58), the most

common finding was “no involvement” (n = 25), followed by occlusion (n = 11), mild (n = 10), moderate (n = 9), and severe involvement (n = 3). In diabetic individuals (n = 29), moderate involvement (n = 7) and occlusion (n = 4) were relatively frequent, with 9 participants showing no involvement. These findings indicate a greater tendency toward moderate to severe involvement and occlusion in diabetic patients.

Diabetic Status * LADA distal Cross tabulation							
Count							
		LADA distal					Total
		no	Mild	moderate	severe	collateral	
Diabetic Status	NO	22	19	6	1	10	58
	YES	15	6	2	0	6	29
Total		37	25	8	1	16	87

Table 3: Representing the Cross-tabulation between diabetic status and LADA distal arterial involvement

Graph 3: Representing the Cross-tabulation between diabetic status and LADA distal arterial involvement

As shown in table 4, In the non-diabetic group (n = 58), the most frequent findings were “no involvement” (n = 22) and “mild involvement” (n = 19), followed by collateral formation (n = 10), moderate (n = 6), and severe involvement (n = 1). Among diabetic patients (n = 29), the most common finding was also “no involvement” (n = 15), followed by collateral (n = 6), mild (n = 6), and moderate involvement (n = 2). No severe involvement was noted in diabetic cases. The distribution suggests that while non-diabetics showed more mild-to-moderate changes, collateral presence was notable in both groups.

Among non-diabetics (n = 58), moderate involvement was most common (n = 17), followed by mild (n = 13), no involvement (n = 16), severe (n = 9), and occlusion (n = 3). In contrast, diabetic individuals (n = 28) showed the highest frequency of “no involvement” (n = 12), followed by severe involvement (n = 8), moderate (n = 3), mild (n = 3), and occlusion (n = 2). These findings suggest a slightly more severe distribution in diabetics despite a lower proportion of moderate involvement.

Among the non-diabetic group (n = 58), “no involvement” was most common (n = 28), followed by moderate (n = 11), mild (n = 10), occlusion (n = 7), and severe (n = 2). In the diabetic group (n = 29), mild involvement was most frequent (n = 11), followed by moderate (n = 7), no involvement (n = 10), and severe (n = 1). No occlusion was reported among diabetic patients. These results show a tendency for diabetics to present more frequently with mild to moderate LCA mid involvement, while occlusion was exclusive to non-diabetic individuals.

Among the non-diabetic group (n = 58), “no involvement” was most common (n = 32), followed by mild (n = 16), collateral (n = 10), and no moderate involvement. In the diabetic group (n = 29), no involvement was still the most frequent category (n = 18), but mild involvement was less common (n = 5), followed by moderate (n = 2), and collateral (n = 4). These results suggest that non-diabetic individuals had a higher frequency of mild and no LCA distal involvement, while diabetic individuals showed a higher proportion of collateral involvement, though the overall involvement was less frequent in comparison.

Cross tabulation		
Count		
	LCA proximal	Total

		No	mild	Moderate	severe	occlusion	
Diabetic Status	NO	16	13	17	9	3	58
	YES	12	3	3	8	2	28
Total		28	16	20	17	5	86
		LCA mid					Total
		no	Mild	moderate	severe	occlusion	
Diabetic Status	NO	28	10	11	2	7	58
	YES	10	11	7	1	0	29
Total		38	21	18	3	7	87
		LCA distal				Total	
		no	mild	moderate	collateral		
Diabetic Status	NO	32	16	0	10	58	
	YES	18	5	2	4	29	
Total		50	21	2	14	87	

Table 4: Representing the Cross-tabulation between diabetic status and LCA arterial involvement. Of the total 87 patients, 33 (37.9%) were not RCA dominant, while 54 (62.1%) were RCA dominant. This indicates that the majority of the patients in the study had RCA dominant involvement.

Among the non-diabetic group (n = 57), the majority had no RCA proximal involvement (n = 40), followed by mild (n = 7), moderate (n = 6), and severe (n = 4). In the diabetic group (n = 29), the distribution was more evenly spread across categories, with no involvement being the most common (n = 18), followed by mild (n = 2), moderate (n = 4), and severe (n = 5). These results suggest that non-diabetic patients more commonly had no or mild RCA proximal involvement, while diabetic patients had a higher proportion of moderate and severe involvement.

Among the non-diabetic group (n = 58), the majority had no RCA mid involvement (n = 28), followed by

mild involvement (n = 18), severe (n = 7), and moderate (n = 5). In the diabetic group (n = 29), no involvement was still the most frequent category (n = 20), followed by mild (n = 3), moderate (n = 4), and severe (n = 2). These results suggest that non-diabetic individuals tended to have a higher proportion of mild and no RCA mid involvement, whereas diabetic individuals had more severe involvement compared to their non-diabetic counterparts.

Among the non-diabetic group (n = 57), the majority had no RCA distal involvement (n = 37), followed by moderate (n = 9), severe (n = 5), and mild (n = 6). In the diabetic group (n = 29), no involvement was still the most frequent category (n = 17), followed by moderate (n = 7), severe (n = 3), and mild (n = 2). These results suggest that non-diabetic individuals had a higher frequency of no or moderate RCA distal involvement, while diabetic individuals had relatively more severe involvement compared to non-diabetic individuals. As shown in table 5

Crosstab						
Count						
		RCA proximal				Total
		no	mild	moderate	severe	
Diabetic Status	NO	40	7	6	4	57
	YES	18	2	4	5	29
Total		58	9	10	9	86

		RCA mid				Total
		No	mild	moderate	severe	
Diabetic Status	NO	28	18	5	7	58
	YES	20	3	4	2	29
Total		48	21	9	9	87
		RCA distal				Total
		no	mild	moderate	severe	
Diabetic Status	NO	37	6	9	5	57
	YES	17	2	7	3	29
Total		54	8	16	8	86

Table 5: Representing the Cross-tabulation between diabetic status and RCA involvement

DISCUSSION

Our study's goal was to use computed tomography angiography (CTA) to compare the features of coronary plaque in patients with and without diabetes. This analytical cross-sectional study was carried out in the radiology department of Fatima Memorial Hospital. Variables like age, gender, diabetes, and patterns of coronary artery involvement were among the data that were statistically examined. CT imaging was used to evaluate the type, distribution, and severity of coronary plaque. Analysis was done on data from 87 patients (mean age: 55.23 ± 8.38 years) between the ages of 40 and 74. The majority of non-diabetic patients had no arterial involvement, especially in the RCA distal, RCA proximal, and LCA distal segments. On the other hand, moderate to severe involvement was more common in diabetic patients, particularly in the RCA mid and LCA mid segments. Only those without diabetes showed occlusions, while collateral formation was more commonly observed in non-diabetic patients in the LCA distal region, occlusions were only seen in non-diabetics. Of the study population, 62.1% had RCA dominant anatomy. Overall, diabetic patients exhibited a pattern of more widespread and severe coronary artery involvement, despite being a smaller group, underscoring the influence of diabetes on the development of plaque. Our study's results are in line with earlier studies that have shown that diabetic patients have more severe coronary involvement. According to Elbassuny and Abdul Fattah (2024), diabetic patients are more likely than non-diabetics to have vulnerable plaque characteristics, such as 100% positive remodeling, Napkin's ring, and low-attenuation plaques. Similarly,

although occlusions were only observed in non-diabetics, diabetic patients in our study exhibited more moderate to severe arterial involvement across multiple coronary segments[3]. Our finding that diabetic patients have a tendency to develop more diffuse and severe coronary disease over time is further supported by Gaillard et al. (2023), who reported that plaque progression over a 10-year follow-up was significantly higher in diabetic patients, with a greater increase in atheroma volume and high-risk plaque features. All of these results highlight how aggressive coronary artery disease is in diabetic patients and how crucial it is to detect it early with imaging techniques like CT angiography¹⁸. In the current study, patients with diabetes were more likely to have moderate to severe coronary artery involvement, especially in the RCA mid and LCA mid segments, than patients without diabetes, who were more likely to have no arterial involvement. This emphasizes the diffuse disease pattern and increased plaque burden linked to diabetes. The predictive value of plaque composition, as opposed to just severity, was the focus of Warren et al. (2024), who discovered that mixed plaque types, which include both calcified and non-calcified components, were more accurate indicators of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACEs) than total plaque burden. While Warren et al.'s findings imply that the precise composition of plaques plays a crucial role in future cardiovascular risk, our study highlights the association between diabetes and more severe and extensive coronary artery disease identified via CTA. When taken as a whole, these findings support the idea that when determining the prognosis of diabetic

patients, both plaque burden and composition must be taken into account¹⁹.

CONCLUSION

Patients with diabetes had more extensive and widespread coronary artery involvement, particularly in the mid and distal LCA and RCA segments. On the other hand, although some displayed occlusion and collateral formation, non-diabetics typically had no or minimal involvement. These findings highlight the need for early intervention in diabetics and continued monitoring in non-diabetics to prevent disease progression.

LIMITATION

- The generalizability of this study is limited by its small sample size and single-institution design. Since it is a cross-sectional study, it does not take into consideration the long-term progression of the disease and only demonstrates associations rather than causality.

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